

STRENGTH PREDICTION OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED INJECTION MOLDINGS

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SUMMARY

Long glass fiber reinforced polypropylene injection moldings were fabricated by using long fiber pellets. AE measurements were performed with two kinds of AE sensors during tensile test. By assuming that the specimen possesses a laminated structure that consists of 0-, 45-, and 90-degree layers, the initial fracture morphologies could be detected.

Keywords: Long fiber pellet, AE measurement, Initial fracture, GFPP, Laminate theory

INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced injection moldings have been widely used in industrial applications. For instance, short glass fiber reinforced polypropylene injection moldings are used in automobile and housings for electrical appliances due to their good mechanical properties [1-2], excellent water resistance and low cost to performance ratio. Recently the growing interest in fiber reinforced injection moldings is the use of high aspect ratio reinforcements, i.e. increasing the length of the fibers in end products, thereby improving the reinforcing ability of the fibers. The long fiber reinforced injection moldings have the potential to be applied not only in the above-mentioned fields but also as structural members.

In order to increase the average fiber length in injection moldings, long fiber pellets have been used recently [3-6]. A pultrusion process is used to manufacture the long fiber pellets. In this process, a continuous reinforcement fiber strand such as glass fiber roving goes through the resin bath, which is filled with melted thermoplastic resin from an extruder. At this moment, the melted thermoplastic resin impregnates into the reinforcement fiber strand. The composite tow would then pass through a water bath to quench the resin. Finally, the tow is cut off to a specific length that is longer than conventional pellets to obtain long-fiber pellets.

In this paper, long glass fiber reinforced polypropylene injection moldings (GFPP) were fabricated by using the above-mentioned long fiber pellets. Acoustic-Emission (AE) measurements were conducted during tensile tests to detect the initial fiber fracture. Moreover, in order to identify the initial fracture morphology detected from AE measurement, a comparison was made between experiment and theoretical values from laminate theory.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Glass fiber (GF) and polypropylene (PP) were used as the reinforcement and matrix, respectively, to manufacture long fiber pellets by the pultrusion process. The length of these pellets was 10 mm, which also represents the length of the GF that are contained within. The content of GF in a pellet was 50 wt%. In order to dilute the content of GF to 20 wt%, these pellets were dry-blended with neat PP pellets (J-900GP, Prime Polymer Co., Ltd.). The materials were injection molded into dumbbell specimens by an injection molding machine (Plaster TM30H, TOYO MACHINERY & METAL Co., Ltd.). The cylinder and mold temperatures were 210 and 30 °C, respectively.

Tensile tests were performed by using an INSTRON universal testing machine (Model 55R4206, INSTRON Co., Ltd.). The grip distance was set at 115 mm and cross-head speed was 10 mm/min. In order to calculate the tensile modulus, an extensometer (Type DYNAMIC, gauge length 50mm, INSTRON Co., Ltd.) was used. At the same time, the AE measurements were also conducted by using two kinds of resonance frequency sensors, i.e. 140 kHz and 1 MHz, to detect the initial fracture during the tensile tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The relationship between tensile stress, accumulative AE events of both sensors and time is shown in Figure 1. The onset of the AE event detected by the 140 kHz and 1 MHz sensors began approximately 7 and 12 seconds, respectively, after the commencement of the tensile test. This indicates that fiber-matrix debonding should have occurred at these times. The tensile modulus, strength and AE generated stress from both sensors are shown in Table 1. The AE generated stress is defined as the stress when the AE event is generated continuously. Therefore, given that the AE generated stress occurred at different times, it is thought that the AE sensors have detected different forms of fracture.

Figure 1: Relationship between tensile stress, accumulative AE events and time

Table 1 Tensile and AE properties

Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	AE generated stress (MPa)	
		140kHz	1MHz
5.14	97.8	30.5	54.1

In order to identify the fracture morphology detected by both AE sensors, the following method was used;

- The injection-molded sample is assumed to possess a 3-layered laminated structure, which is embedded with fibers oriented at 0, 45 and 90 degrees to the resin flow axis.
- Initial fracture stresses of the 45- and 90-degree layers are also assumed.
- The initial fracture stresses in the 45- and 90-degree layers are calculated by using the laminate theory.
- Experimental (AE generated stress) and calculated values were compared.

In order to determine the thickness of each layer, the fiber orientation angle along the flow direction was measured. First, the specimen was cut along the transverse direction. Then, cross-sectional observation was performed and photographs were taken. A typical photograph of the cross-section is shown in Figure 2. From these photographs, fiber orientation angle was calculated from the aspect ratio of the glass fibers. The distribution of fiber orientation angle is shown in Figure 3. Figure 3(a) shows the distribution of fiber orientation angle at every 5 degrees. From these results, fibers oriented at 0 to 15 degrees, 15 to 75 degrees, and 75 to 90 degrees are assumed to represent the 0-degree, 45-degree and 90-degree layers, respectively [7]. The distribution of fibers according to the respective layers is shown in Figure 3(b) whereby the frequency represents the thickness of each layer since the volume fraction of glass fiber is assumed to be constant throughout the specimen.

Figure 2: Photograph of TD cross-section

Figure 3: Distribution of fiber orientation angle: (a) distribution at every 5 degrees (b) distribution at 0, 45 and 90 degrees

In the case of the 90-degree layer, glass fibers are mostly oriented perpendicular to the flow direction, which is comparable to a weld line. Therefore, the initial fracture of the 90-degree layer is considered to be due to the debonding between GF and PP. According to our previous studies, the initial fracture stress of a weld line in GF/PP composites was approximately 15 MPa [8]. Hence, the initial fracture stress of the 90-degree layer was assumed to be 15 MPa. In the case of the 45-degree layer, the principal fracture mode should be shear fracture. Hence, initial fracture of 45-degree layer was considered as shear fracture at the GF/PP interface. The interfacial shear strength was calculated by Kelly-Tyson's equation [9] and the relationship between interfacial shear strength and critical fiber length is expressed through the following equation:

$$\sigma_{comp}^* = F \cdot \sigma_f^* \left\{ \sum_{l_i > l_c} \left(1 - \frac{l_c}{2l_i} \right) V_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l_j < l_c} \left(\frac{l_j}{l_c} \right) V_j \right\} + \sigma_m^* (1 - V_f) \quad (1)$$

$$l_c = \frac{d \cdot \sigma_f^*}{2\tau} \quad (2)$$

- σ_{comp}^* : Strength of composites τ_i : Interfacial shear strength
 l_c : Critical fiber length d : Diameter of fiber
 l : Fiber length σ_m^* : Strength of matrixes
 σ_f^* : Strength of fibers V_f : Volume fraction of fiber
 V_i : Volume fraction of fiber, Fiber length < l_c V_j : Volume fraction fiber, Fiber length > l_c
 F : Coefficient of fiber orientation

The main parameters to calculate the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) are shown in Table 2. Here, the calculation method of Krenchel et al. [10] is used to obtain the coefficient of fiber orientation. The fiber length distribution in the specimens was also measured. Samples were obtained from the dumbbell specimens after tensile test. The fractured specimen was cut 5 mm from the fractured region and pyrolyzed in a muffle furnace at 600 °C for 4 hours to obtain the residual glass fibers. The length of these glass fibers was measured by image analysis (COSMOS32, Library Co., Ltd.) and the distribution is shown in Figure 4. From these data, the IFSS is determined to be 19.1 MPa, which can be also assumed to be the initial fracture stress of the 45-degree layer.

The strain of the 90-degree layer was obtained when the stress of this layer reaches 15 MPa. Subsequently, this strain was used to calculate the stress needed for fiber-matrix debonding in the laminate structure by using the laminate theory. Hence, the fiber-matrix debonding stress is determined to be 31.6 MPa. From the IFSS calculation, the stress of the 45-degree layer is determined to be 19.1 M Pa. Again, by using laminate theory, the stress needed to cause interfacial shear fracture across the laminate structure can be calculated and was determined to be 58.0 MPa.

Table 2 Parameter for Kelly-Tyson's equation

σ_c^* (MPa)	σ_f^* (GPa)	σ_m^* (MPa)	d (μm)	F
97.8	34.5	33.1	13	0.51

The calculated fiber-matrix debonding stress, which is 31.6 MPa, agrees well to the AE generated stress that was detected by the 140 kHz sensor (30.5 MPa). Meanwhile, the calculated interfacial shear fracture across the laminate structure, which is 58.0 MPa, agrees well with the AE generated stress detected by the 1 MHz sensor (54.1 MPa). This indicates that the 140 kHz and 1MHz sensors could detect debonding and interfacial shear fracture between GF and PP, respectively.

Figure 4: Fiber length distribution

CONCLUSION

In this paper, long glass fiber reinforced polypropylene injection moldings were fabricated by using long fiber pellets. By simultaneously using two kinds of AE sensors, i.e. 140 kHz and 1 MHz, AE measurements were performed during tensile test. By assuming that the specimen possesses a laminated structure that consists of 0-, 45-, and 90-degree layers, the initial fracture morphologies could be detected by two AE sensors. It was concluded that the initial fractures that could be detected by the 140 kHz and 1 MHz sensors were delamination and interfacial shear fracture between GF and PP, respectively.

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